

Evaluation and comparison of selected methodologies to investigate occupational accidents

Salguero-Caparrros, Francisco, Rubio-Romero, Juan Carlos

Abstract.

BACKGROUND: The choice of the “right” methodology to carry out the occupational accident investigation process is not an easy task. Each methodology has different conceptual and practical characteristics. The choice will depend to a large extent on the conceptual accident model being used.

OBJECTIVE: The aim of this study has been to evaluate and compare a set of nine methodologies recognised as the most widely used in the field of occupational accident investigation.

METHODS: For this purpose, six evaluation criteria are used which have already been applied and validated by the scientific community with a clear emphasis on the holistic nature of these methodologies.

RESULTS: The results show a detailed analysis of the conceptual, methodological and practical characteristics of the nine selected occupational accident investigation methodologies. The conceptual framework of each of the methodologies, their holistic characteristics in terms of whether they cover the complete information cycle and its possible interrelation, reliability and validity of the methodologies, the experience required for their application, the flexibility in terms of being able to be used in different work environments and finally the ability of the methodology to motivate organisational improvement are presented.

CONCLUSIONS: From this study, it is clear that the analysis of occupational accident investigation it is becoming increasingly necessary to employ scientific methodologies with a clear proactive approach in order to meet the challenges of changing socio-technical systems.